

Perspective-based Specification of Machine Learning-enabled Systems

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* Required

Demographics

1. For each level of education below, please specify whether you have completed it and the name of the course:

Undergraduate

Your answer _____

Specialization

Your answer _____

Master

Your answer _____

Ph.D

Your answer _____

Other

Your answer _____

2. If any, what further training / formation directly related to machine learning did you receive?

Your answer _____

3. What is the size of the organization you currently work for? *

- 1-10 employees
- 11-50 employees
- 51-250 employees
- 251-500 employees
- 501-1,000 employees
- 1,001-2,000 employees
- More than 2,000 employees

4. Which role best describes your current activities within the company? *

- Project Lead / Project Manager
- Business Analyst
- Requirements Engineer
- Solution Architect
- Data Scientist
- Developer
- Test Manager / Tester
- Other: _____

5. How many years of experience do you have in developing ML-based projects? *

Your answer _____

6. How many ML-based projects have you participated in? Please, provide your best estimate: *

Your answer _____

7. Considering the ML-based projects in which you participated, what is the average team size? *

- 1 member
- 2 - 5 members
- 6 - 10 members
- 10 + members

8. Considering the ML-based projects in which you participated, which project management frameworks were applied? *

- To the best of my knowledge, none
- CRISP-DM
- Kanban
- Lean
- RUP/Open UP
- SAFe
- Scrum
- Other: _____

9. Considering the ML-based projects in which you participated, how agile do you rate your ML-based system development? *

- Totally agile
- Mostly agile
- Balanced between agile and traditional
- Mostly traditional
- Totally traditional

10. Considering the ML-based projects in which you participated, to which application domains are they related? *

- Banking/Financial
- Defence & Security
- Education
- Embedded systems in Automotive or Avionics
- Entertainment
- Healthcare
- Insurance
- Logistics
- Oil & Gas
- Sales/E-commerce
- Telecommunication
- Other: _____

11. In case of any additional suggestion, please do not hesitate to let us know it

Your answer _____

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